

Teaching functions to 21st-century mathematics learners through a real-life problem

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Over a few decades now, educators all over the world are contemplating “How teaching-learning of mathematics should be?”. In the 21st century, mathematics holds a special place due to the increased demands of skills that mathematics impart. Three major guiding ideas of 21st-century mathematics teaching are (a) Learning in a context, (b) Learning for the 21st century, and (c) Reducing the gap between school math and real life. This poster aims to provide a way to design a problem-based learning environment by posing a real-life problem in a high school classroom, specifically discussing the Vehicle routing problem designed around the day-to-day environment of students. This context of the problem will initiate the discussion among students and the facilitator on mathematical ideas around functions. This approach will provide a way for learners to understand the underlying mathematics of the real-life scenario under investigation.

Introduction

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 2003 argued due to huge social changes and an explosion of knowledge in the 21st-century there is a dire need to change the fundamental units of education. The concept of formal education in the 21st century is characterized by the idea of the knowledge economy and globalization processes. In this century learners are expected to work towards generating new ideas and solve complex problems. According to OECD, these independent learners must acquire core competencies known as 21st-century skills to make them ready for future challenges of the 21st-century.

Mathematical competencies have been given a central position among the skills that are required by learners to thrive in the 21st century. A study (Gravemeijer et al., 2017) on future mathematical competencies required in a workplace explores what mathematics education prepares students for the future. The study suggests that modeling and applications should be one of the major goals for mathematics education, where learners can gain experience to devise solutions to an authentic real-life problem hence understanding the underlying mathematics.

Another research by the Advisory Committee on Mathematics Education (ACME) in 2011 shows how themes of mathematical modeling, costing, calculating risk, and quality control

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processes make up a huge portion of today's workplace. Through one on one interviews with employees (25 companies in the United Kingdom) across the sectors of employment, ACME has concluded that in a workplace more than the application of mathematics one should be able to solve problems within a context and communicate it effectively. They also recommend identified themes to be incorporated into the mathematics curriculum of the country.

This made us question:

1. What are the guiding ideas of 21st-century mathematics teaching? and
2. How can we design learning in a mathematical classroom that makes learners ready for the 21st century?

Taking a hint from aforementioned studies, we framed major guiding ideas for 21st-century mathematics teaching as (a) Learning for the 21st century, (b) Learning in a context, and (c) Making school mathematics workplace-ready i.e reducing the gap between school math and real life.

One of the possible solutions for our second question is provided by the pedagogy of problem-based learning (PBL) which has been gaining momentum lately. It is a blend of various past approaches (Hmelo-Silver et al., 2006) that had their influences on PBL during its development phases. Educators believe that problem-based learning has drawn inspiration majorly from (a) Constructivist Approach to Learning, (b) Critical Theory/Critical Pedagogy, and (c) Pragmatism (Hirschman et al., 2018; National Council of Educational Research and Training, 2005; Savin-Baden et al., 2004).

PBL is a learner-centered approach that believes: a learner constructs knowledge while resolving a real-world ill-structured problem. PBL promotes the importance of peer-learning by enabling learners to work in collaboration. Throughout the process of resolving a problem a learner plays different roles (Savin-Baden et al., 2004, pp. 81–92) such as real-world problem solver, critical thinker, communicator and self-directed learners.

Keeping in mind the pedagogy of PBL and suggestions given in “The Role of Contexts in the Mathematics Classroom: Do They Make Mathematics More ‘Real’?” (Boaler, 1993), the author has designed an activity. The objective of this project was to develop a lesson plan for the PBL environment to introduce the concept of functions to Indian high school students.

About the lesson plan

The lesson plan was developed to introduce the concept of functions to high school students. The topic skills that were taken into consideration before designing a problem statement are (a) Identifying independent and dependent variables, (b) Identifying the mathematical relationship between variables, (c) Designing a mathematical function from mathematical relation, (d) Domain and Range of a function, (e) Graph of the function, (f) Nature of graph of function and (g) Finding optimal solutions graphically.

The expected time to fulfill the objectives of the plan was kept 1.5 weeks. Understanding of the cartesian plane is the prerequisite knowledge required for this activity.

Choice of problem

Boaler, J., 1993 identifies contexts as general motivators to students which keep their interest going. But sometimes if a problem is an interpretation of a “real-life” scenario that expects students to enter a fantasy world they tend to think of it as some other textbook math problem. She also states “Using the real world, local community, and even individualized examples which students may analyze and interpret is thought to present mathematics as a means with which to understand reality. This allows students to become involved with mathematics and to break down their perceptions of a remote body of knowledge” (Boaler, 1993, p. 13).

On the other hand, Mauffette et al. (2004, pp. 11–25) explored the connection between the problem and the motivation of the students in a problem-based learning environment. Their findings suggest that initially for an introductory PBL level the facilitator should clearly identify and summarize the problem instead of putting it in a wider context which is the next level and is suitable for senior PBL learners. They also recommend that background information should be drawn from one source of data and information about the settings should be complete without omitting the details.

Optimization is one of the concepts we use often. In our day-to-day life from choosing a path to our destination or ordering food either we maximize or minimize certain quantities. Indian National Curriculum Framework 2005 put forward connecting knowledge to the outside world as one of the visions of mathematics education in the country. Choosing a problem that is deeply connected with the learners’ life where the topic skills can be mapped was chosen, for the context Vehicle routing problem was finalized.

Figure 1: Map followed during the activity.

Note: The map was based on the locality students are familiar with.

Problem statement

“Using the map, find the best routes to reach point A to B in such a way you have to spend minimum time while covering all the highlighted places at least once.”

In this, students are expected to answer: (a) Variables in the context, (b) Variables affecting the time, (c) Developing the understanding of their time function, (d) Representing their models on a cartesian plane, (e) Justifying their calculations, and (f) Finding accuracy in comparison with the estimated time given in Google Maps (see Fig. 1).

Critical discussions during the activity:

1. While finding variables both dependent and independent, the relationship between the mode of covering the distance (walking, running, cycling etc.), traffic encountered, and time spent will be discussed.
2. Interpreting mode of covering the distance in numerical terms.
3. Depending upon students' approach/approaches different data sets will be obtained hence resulting in different functions.
4. Finding optimal solutions from the datasets obtained.

The rationale to the conference theme

Using problem-based learning for introducing concepts will help teachers to make mathematical learning relatable to learners and they will see how mathematics is a part of their life. Using PBL they will also help their learners to develop 21st-century skills. In the present time all over the world, there is a need for resources for mathematical teaching and learning which help learners to understand the underlying mathematics while interacting with real-life problems. When it comes to PBL, not many resources are available for teachers to implement in their classrooms. This presentation provides one way of designing a PBL environment in fulfilling the objective of mathematics education in the 21st century. It can be placed in the theme ‘Sociology of Mathematics Education’ of the conference as this presentation will talk about a new approach to teaching functions.

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